

D6.2. Testing methodology and test plan

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About ThrombUS+

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is the formation of a blood clot within the deep veins, most commonly those of the lower limbs, causing obstruction of blood flow. In 50% of people with DVT, the clot eventually breaks off and travels to the lung to cause pulmonary embolism. Clinical assessment of DVT is notoriously unreliable because up to 2/3 of DVT episodes are clinically silent and patients are symptom free even when pulmonary embolism has developed. Early diagnosis of DVT is crucial and despite the progress made in ultrasound imaging and plethysmography techniques, there is a need for new methods to enable continuous monitoring DVT diagnosis at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on a novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally.

ThrombUS+ is intended for use by postoperative patients in the ward, during long surgical operations, cancer patients or otherwise bedridden patients at home or in care units, and women during pregnancy and postpartum. ThrombUS+ will use big data sets for AI training collected in the project via 3 large scale clinical studies and will validate the outcome in the clinical setting via 1 early feasibility study and 1 multi-center clinical trial.

Deliverable D6.2 Description

Deliverable D6.2 is a direct output of Task 6.2. Task 6.2 aims to generate a rigorous testing methodology and design a testing plan to demonstrate that ThrombUS+ system meets requirements identified in T2.3, and the relevant regulations and standards analyzed in T2.2. It includes the general process for performing the testing, documenting evidence of testing and the process for handling testing failures, including feedback to the design. Testing will address individual modules of the alpha-prototype of the entire ThrombUS + system and then focus on the integrated beta-prototype. The deliverable details the types of tests, descriptions of specific test environments, who is responsible for the specific tests, equipment or instruments used, and other organisational requirements, and involve ergonomic assessment based on T7.4. The task is led by KTU, an expert in sensor and sensor technology hardware and software development and testing. The regulatory partner VDE has a crucial role to ensure that compliance by design aspects are defined. All partners participate to ensure continuity with the rest of the project activities.

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Terms and Definitions

Term	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CDUS	Compression Duplex Ultrasound
DVT	Deep Vein Thrombosis
EAC	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Electronic Actuator Controller
EC	European Commission
EIM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Electrical Impedance Module
EIP	Electrical Impedance Plethysmography
EU	European Union
HIS	Health Information Systems
LAM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Limb Activity Module
LRM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Light Rheography Module
LRR	Light Reflection Rheography
RUCs	Reference Use Cases
SDK	Software Development Kit
UI	User Interface
US	Ultrasound
USM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Ultrasound Monitoring Module
VOP	Venous Occlusion Plethysmography
WAM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Wearable Actuator Module
XGM	Identifier for ThrombUS+ Extended Reality and Serious Gaming Module
XRG	Extended Reality and Serious Gaming subsystem for DVT prevention.

Executive Summary

Deliverable D6.2, outlines the comprehensive testing methodology and detailed test plan for the ThrombUS+ system. It serves as a critical framework for demonstrating that the system aligns with identified requirements. The deliverable specifically focuses on two crucial pre-clinical testing phases: **System Integration Testing** and **System Readiness Testing**.

System Integration Testing involves evaluating the functionality and interaction of the ThrombUS+ system's seven modules: the Central Hub & Intelligence (CHI), Ultrasound Monitoring (USM), Wearable Actuator (WAM), Electrical Impedance (EIM), Light Rheography (LRM), Limb Activity (LAM), and Extended Reality and Serious Gaming (XGM). This phase validates the device's four functional working methods for DVT monitoring and prevention by testing high-level workflows and module interactions at both hardware and software levels. Test cases are designed to evaluate specific system requirements, ensuring successful integration and proper functioning of components.

System Readiness Testing involves comprehensive evaluation of the entire integrated ThrombUS+ device using the Central Hub & Intelligence unit, replicating real-world working modes. Beyond functional requirements, this phase rigorously assesses user safety, information security, data privacy, connection stability, and overall system robustness and reliability. Successful completion of these tests signifies that the system meets all user and system requirements, is safe and reliable, and is ready for progression to human clinical trials.

Performance indicators are defined by the successful achievement of expected outcomes for each "Test Case." Any testing failures are subject to a systematic Root Cause Analysis (RCA) to identify sources of error and implement corrective actions. This ensures device safety and regulatory compliance.

The comprehensive pre-clinical testing outlined in this document is essential for generating data to support progression to human clinical trials and ultimately securing regulatory review and approval.

1. Introduction

Deliverable T6.2 presents the testing methodology and the test plan to demonstrate that the ThrombUS+ integrated system meets the user and system requirements identified in T2.3 and complies with relevant regulations and standards identified in T2.2. This process is crucial, as careful planning, documenting and implementing rigorous tests will enable the identification of potential gaps either in the development of the various alpha prototypes or during their integration.

The development methodology of the ThrombUS+ system follows a generic V-model based on Figure 1. The model describes system development as consisting of three phases:

- 1| design–verification,
- 2| system building, and
- 3| testing–verification.

However, these phases are not strictly unidirectional. Various testing steps introduce recursion and may lead to iterations in the system development process (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The V-model diagram of systems engineering¹.

In this model the testing steps in the different developmental phases are defined as:

- 1) Unit testing: This phase primarily involves laboratory testing of the developed prototypes and sub-modules. It includes the use of mechanical and electrical measurements, to verify whether each component meets its specific requirements. These tests are expected to be conducted and reported within the relative prototype development tasks, and the respective work packages (WP3, WP4, and WP5).
- 2) System integration testing: During this phase, comprehensive tests of integrated submodules are conducted to validate their expected functionality. In addition, the integration between specific testing submodules can be tested. The methodology and planning of these tests are described in this deliverable.

¹ "System Engineering, integration and requirements management tool.," Reqi. Accessed: Jun. 08, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://reqi.io/>

- 3) System readiness testing: This phase refers to testing of the entire integrated system to validate the overall functionality of the system based on the user and system requirements. These tests aim to ensure that the functionality of the entire system is robust and as expected, before progressing to production or clinical use. The methodology and planning of these tests are described in this deliverable.
- 4) Acceptance Testing: During this phase testing is performed by end users (i.e., medical personnel and patients) to verify and validate that the system functions as expected in the production (i.e., clinical environment). These tests are scheduled to be carried out during the clinical studies work package (WP7), and their methodology and planning are outside the scope of this deliverable.

This delivery focuses on the system integration testing and system readiness testing (steps #2 and #3 in the above list). These stages are critical for validating that the integrated ThrombUS+ system functions as intended, meet all defined user and system requirements and is safe and reliable for use in a clinical environment. Successfully completing these phases will allow the device to move forward in the next phase of the clinical trials and be tested in a real-world scenario by a user.

2. Testing methodology

Based on the overall system architecture the ThrombUS+ system consists of seven different modules, namely the Central Hub & Intelligence (CHI) module, the Ultrasound Monitoring Module (USM), the Wearable Actuator Module (WAM), the Electrical Impedance Module (EIM), the Light Rheography Module (LRM), the Limb Activity Module (LAM) and the Extended Reality and Serious Gaming Module (XGM)(Figure 2)².

Figure 2. The ThrombUS+ device is composed of seven modules. Except the CHI, and XRG, all other modules consist of both hardware and software.

During real-world operation, the combination of these modules gives rise to four functional working methods for the operator-independent DVT-monitoring and DVT prevention, as described in detail within deliverable D6.1. To implement each functional working mode, the different modules should interact, both at hardware

² Marozas V, Portokallidis N, Jurkonis R, Jucevičius M, Eitminavičius R, Lukoševičius A, Daukantas S, Rapalis A, Sonda A, Moutafidou A, Cesana J, Moustakidis P, Lange N, Balling S, Querengässer J, Legros M, Novikov D, Maja S, Prinz T, Kaldoudi E. Product Design Specifications, Deliverable 6.1, ThrombUS+ Horizon Europe Innovation Action, EC Grant Agreement No. 101137227, 28 February 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14930624>

and software levels. For example, implementing the operator-independent Compression Ultrasound Duplex Ultrasound (CDUS) method requires the integration of the Ultrasound Monitoring Module, the Wearable Actuator Module, the Limb Activity module, the Extended Reality & Serious Gaming module and the Central Hub & Intelligence unit. An effort to integrate and test all these modules for their full functionality at once, while development is in process, is practically impossible and poses significant risks.

To account for this complexity, our testing methodology is structured around these four functional working methods, which form the basis of the overall validation process. For each functional working method, we have defined a high-level workflow that introduces an appropriate level of abstraction. This methodology simplifies integration efforts and reduces testing complexity.

During the system the system integration phase, module interaction and functionality will be tested based on the high-level workflows. In the subsequent readiness testing phase, the whole integrated device, consisting of all modules, will be tested for safety, performance, and functional requirements.

2.1. System integration testing phase

For each high-level workflow several steps have been defined (Figure 4 - Figure 7). All these steps will be followed to evaluate the overall performance of the respective subsystems. Each step is defined as a “Test case” which evaluates one or more system requirements from the overall ThrombUS+ system. To implement these test cases, Graphical User Interfaces (GUIs) and the Software Development Kits (SDKs) developed for the individual modules can be utilized instead of the Central Hub & Intelligence unit.

A similar approach will be followed to test the frontend and backend core functionalities of the Central Hub & Intelligence module. However, in this case each “Test case” consists of various steps that should be followed. These steps mainly consist of user interactions with the main application interface for testing the different application components of Central Hub & Intelligence and evaluating one or more system requirements relating to the Central Hub & Intelligence unit before the integration with the other modules.

2.2. System Readiness Testing phase

During this testing phase, the whole integrated ThrombUS+ device will be tested. All tests at this stage should be conducted strictly by utilizing the Central Hub & Intelligence unit, and must replicate the exact working modes, as defined in the system architecture deliverable. In addition to the functionality tests, special attention should be given to user safety, information security and privacy, connection loss, and the overall robustness and reliability of the ThrombUS+ device. Passing successfully these testing phase, will allow the Thrombus+ device to further be evaluated in a clinical setting.

2.3. Performance indicators

The primary objective of the testing process is to verify that all defined requirements are met. During the system integration testing phase, each step in the workflow defines a “Test Case”. Each “Test Case” is designed to evaluate one or more specific system requirements. If the expected outcomes of each “Test Case” are achieved, the associated system requirements are considered fulfilled. Successfully passing all “Test Cases” indicates that the respective components have been integrated successfully, they function properly and are ready for further integration and testing.

Similarly, expected results have been defined for the phase of system readiness testing. However, if, during this phase, all expected outcomes are achieved, together with the results of unit testing and system integration testing, all system requirements will be covered successfully. This demonstrates that the fully integrated system covers all user requirements and performs as intended. At this stage the device will be ready for deployment in clinical settings.

If the expected results of a “Test Case” cannot be achieved, this should be documented, and the failure will be handled according to Chapter 2.6 of this document.

2.4. Testing timeline and responsibilities

The testing will be carried out according to the terms set out in the Gantt chart of WP6 and the specific tasks therein (Table 1). While a lead partner has been assigned for each task, the contribution and the feedback from all partners is essential, given the complexity and interdependence of the subsystems.

Table 1. Testing timeline.

No.	Task	Due Month	Lead partner	Participants
T6.3	Hardware integration and testing	M26 – February 2026	KTU	VDE, all
T6.4	Software integration and development of the central intelligence module and app	M28 – April 2026	ATHENA	VDE, PBY, all
T6.5	Hardware and software integration, communications, security, and privacy	M32 – August 2026	KTU	ATHENA, VDE, all

2.5. Required equipment and instruments

In both testing phases, various phantoms will be utilized to perform the appropriate tests.

For testing the Compression Duplex Ultrasound (CDUS) working mode, the professional “SONOtrain Ultrasound Vein Model” (3B scientific, Germany) phantom will be used, to ensure uniform testing. The phantom enables reproducible testing of tissue compression and is also used to assess ultrasound transducers and beamformers for image quality, ensuring clear visualization of anatomical structures.

For testing the Venous Occlusion Plethysmography (VOP) an electrical circuit phantom will be used. This approach enables rapid and convenient testing with different phantoms, simulating various working conditions.

The Extended Reality & Serious Gaming working mode will be tested using a custom, 3D printed (using Ultimaker S5, 0.4mm head) phantom leg, which allows for a similar movement and positioning of the real leg, allowing the fixation of three sensors imitating three different positions on the leg: thigh, shin, and foot. This allows for a reproducible and controllable testing of IMU’s signal quality, quaternions, and estimated angles and leg position, as well as testing and evaluating the extended reality environment.

In exceptional cases and only if no alternative tests are feasible, healthy volunteers from within the project may be involved in validating the performance of integrated modules. Such tests will be conducted after ensuring that the devices are safety and the system poses no risk of harm to the user. If required, ethical approval will be requested by the relevant institutional ethics committee. It is important to note that neither of the ThombUS+ functional working methods are considered interventional.

2.6. Handling testing failures

Systematic Root Cause Analysis (RCA)³ is used to identify failure sources. RCA process integrates structured frameworks – a cross-disciplinary team engaging engineers and clinicians, having a cross-functional expertise, and includes iterative testing—transformation of failures into actionable insights, ensuring device safety and

³ Root Cause Analysis (RCA) in Testing: ‘Detect,’ ‘Analyze,’ and ‘Improve’: Jun. 19, 2025. [Online]. Available <https://www.lambdatest.com/blog/rca-in-testing/>

regulatory compliance. In pre-clinical tests, only device-related failures are concerned. Minor and major failure sources could be related to device software and/or hardware flaws, test operator/human errors, facility/environment (e.g., electromagnetic interference), and inadequate test procedure. After RCA-based identification of test failure, corrective actions are taken. The main concern in tackling test failures is patient safety, since certain failure consequences could be harmful.

If a minor failure is identified, and RCA analysis shows a particular device-related failure source, the problem in prototype hardware/software is fixed, and the test is repeated until it passes. If the test failure source or sources are different, testing is provided iteratively, engaging several test operators, changing the environment, and/or correcting the test steps.

When a major device failure is identified, and conventional fixing attempts of prototype problems fail, it causes a redesign of the alpha prototype and iterative retesting. In critical cases, the testing procedure and/or requirements could be minimally corrected, ultimately maintaining the meeting of system and user requirements.

Figure 3. The block diagram of testing failure management.

Test failures are documented and analysed. A methodical approach—combining RCA, scientific justification, and regulatory collaboration—enables project developers to rectify issues efficiently while ensuring patient safety and compliance.

2.7. Documentation of testing

Testing activities will be documented based on the “Test_case_report_documentation” template as provided in Annex 2. To ensure traceability and transparency, each “Test Case” is assigned a unique identifier, which links it directly to the corresponding system requirement(s) and test results.

2.8. The usage of test results for the advancement of the ThrombUS+ system

The test results generated through this comprehensive testing methodology serve as critical input for the iterative advancement and optimization of the ThrombUS+ system. Beyond validating compliance with technical specifications and regulatory requirements, the testing outcomes provide essential feedback mechanisms that drive system refinement across all four subsystems. Performance data, failure analysis, and usability assessments inform design modifications, algorithm enhancements, and user interface improvements that enhance the system’s clinical effectiveness and user experience. The systematic documentation and analysis of test results enable evidence-based decision-making for product development

and establish benchmark metrics for future system iterations. Ongoing analysis of test results ensures that risk management processes remain aligned with clinical evaluations, minimizing the likelihood of adverse events and regulatory non-compliance. Furthermore, the testing data contributes to the development of clinical validation protocols and supports the creation of comprehensive user training materials, ensuring that the ThrombUS+ system not only meets current requirements but also evolves to address emerging clinical needs and technological opportunities in deep vein thrombosis detection and monitoring.

3. Testing plan

3.1. System integration testing plan

3.1.1. High – level testing of Compression Duplex Ultrasonography

The high-level testing for the Compression Duplex ultrasonography (CSUS) is based on the workflow presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. High level workflow for testing the Compression Duplex Ultrasonography. Integration between Ultrasound and Wearable Actuator modules will be tested independently from AI/ML testing.

It should be noted that in the final system the AI/ML model for automatic DVT detection will be integrated in the Ultrasound model. However, during this stage they will be tested separately. Therefore, according to Figure 4, steps 1, 2.1, 2.2, 5, 6, 9, 10 will be followed for testing the integration of the Ultrasound Module (without AI) with the Wearable Actuator module. These tests will be implemented using technical graphical user interfaces (GUIs) instead of the Central Hub & Intelligence module. This GUI integrates the ultrasound’s software development kit (SDK) and the actuator’s SDK. To simulate the automated compression/decompression process that will be followed in the final device, the feedback control of compression is implemented by estimating strain as a response of tissues that surround the vessels of interest. The region-averaged strain versus time is calculated from ultrasonic radiofrequency signals backscattered from tissues, and when a default threshold is reached, decompression starts.

On the other hand, tests regarding AI/ML model integration will be conducted separately using the Central Hub & Intelligence unit (steps 3, 4, 7, 8) (Figure 4). These tests focus on the compatibility between the Central Hub and the machine learning models. Simulated data will be used to check the data flow towards and from the AI/ML model.

The steps to be followed for testing the integration between the Ultrasound module (without AI/ML) and the Wearable Actuator module using a technical GUI are presented in Table 2. Test results are based on both hardware and software compatibility with the components.

Table 2. High-level workflow of CDUS for testing the integration between the Ultrasound Module (without AI) and the Wearable Actuator Module.

Work flow step	Description	Test case ID	System requirement	Expected results
1	Compression Duplex Ultrasound method is initialized by pressing the “Start” button in the GUI. The SDK from the ultrasound sends a command to start image acquisition.	TC_CDUS_01	SR_PR01_USM_08	Image acquisition can be started utilizing ultrasound’s SDK.
2.1	USM starts streaming images to the computer (technical GUI).	TC_CDUS_02	SR_PR01_USM_17	Images can be sent to computer (GUI) utilizing ultrasound’s SDK.
2.2	Synchronously with each acquired frame, USM sends synchronization signal to WAM, so it can synchronize pressure measurements to images.	TC_CDUS_03	SR_PR01_USM_05	Trigger signals are sent to the compression actuator from the ultrasound.
5	The GUI receives these outputs and sends the “Start_Inflation” command to the WAM using the WAM SDK.	TC_CDUS_04	SR_PR01_WAM_02 SR_PR01_WAM_04 SR_PR01_WAM_06 SR_PR01_WAM_08	Inflation can be initialized via WAM’s SDK.
6	WAM starts inflation and starts either periodically (if a sync signal is received) or on demand, sending pressure values to the GUI, for pressuring monitoring.	TC_CDUS_05	SR_PR01_WAM_06	Current pressure levels are returned from the WAM to the computer (GUI) via the SDK.
9	Based on strain measurements, or maximum allowed pressure, the GUI send the “Stop_Inflation” command to WAM, if predefined thresholds have been reached.	TC_CDUS_06	SR_PR01_WAM_06	Terminate inflation signal can be sent to the WAM, via it’s SDK, upon user’s request or upon maximum allowed pressure levels are reached.
10	The GUI terminates the image acquisition by sending the “STOP” command to the USM, finalizing the CDUS method.	TC_CDUS_07	SR_PR01_USM_17	Upon receiving the “STOP” command from the computer (GUI), ultrasound terminates image acquisition and stops triggering the WAM.

The steps to be followed for testing the integration between the Central Hub & Intelligence module and the AI/ML model for automated DVT detection Table 3. These test results are based on software compatibility between the two components.

Table 3. High-level workflow of CDUS for testing the integration between the AI/ML model and the Central Hub & Intelligence Module.

Work flow step	Description	Test case ID	System requirement	Expected results
3	CHI feeds simulation ultrasound images to the AI/ML model.	TC_CDUS_08	SR_PRO1_USM_13 SR_PRO1_USM_14	Images are in the appropriate format for the AI/ML model.
4	The AI software module processes the received image and returns the model outputs: cross-sections of target vessels, image quality grade. Final decision whether input image is of diagnostic value or not is returned to the CHI.	TC_CDUS_09	SR_PRO1_USM_13 SR_PRO1_USM_14	AI/ML model returns the inference results to the CHI.
7	CHI feeds simulation ultrasound images pressure levels to the AI/ML model.	TC_CDUS_10	SR_PRO1_USM_13 SR_PRO1_USM_14	Images are in the appropriate format for the AI/ML model.
8	AI software module processes received image and pressure levels and returns required parameters as outputs: vein cross-section, image quality grading. Decision on whether to stop inflation or whether DVT presence or not are also returned to CHI.	TC_CDUS_11	SR_PRO1_USM_13 SR_PRO1_USM_14	AI/ML model returns the inference results and decisions to the CHI.

3.1.2. High – Level testing of Venous Occlusion Plethysmography

The Venous Occlusion Plethysmography (VOP) method is implemented by integrating the Electrical Impedance Module (EIM) and the Wearable Actuator Module (WAM), for implementing the electrical impedance measurements and the venous occlusion, respectively. The Electrical Impedance Module measures body impedance in bipolar or tetrapolar configuration using the textile band electrodes. It allows for two measurement modalities, with the ability to transfer data to the controlling off-the-self computer over a Wi-Fi link. The Wearable Actuator Module, when commanded, performs inflation and rapid deflation of the thigh cuff – an essential step in performing the VOP test. AI/ML models will be utilized for interpreting data and deciding whether DVT is present or not. The Central Hub & Intelligence module will serve an intermediate between the above-mentioned components. To ease integration and testing, the high-level functional workflow for the Venous Occlusion Plethysmography method is presented in Figure 5. Although, the AI/ML models belong to the Electrical Impedance Module, at this stage they will be tested separately. First, the integration between the Electrical Impedance Module (Electrodes and Electrical Impedance Controller) and the Wearable Actuator Module will be tested via the utilization of technical Graphical User Interfaces (GUIs), instead of using the Central Hub & Intelligence module (steps 1, 2, 3.1, 3.2, 4, 5) (Table 4). During these steps, the compatibility between the hardware and software of the components will be evaluated. Secondly, the integration tests between the Central Hub & Intelligence module and the AI/ML models for the electrical impedance measurements. These tests will be conducted to evaluate software compatibility between the two components (steps 6, 7) (Table 5).

Figure 5. High – level workflow of the Venous Occlusion Plethysmography. Integration between Ultrasound and Wearable Actuator modules will be tested independently from AI/ML testing.

Table 4. High-level workflow of VOP for testing the integration between the Electrical Impedance Module (without AI) and the Wearable Actuator Module.

Work flow step	Description	Test case ID	System requirement	Expected results
1	By pressing the “Start” button in the technical GUI, the VOP method is initialized, utilizing Electrical Impedance Module’s SDK, and signal acquisition starts.	TC_VOP_01	SR_PRO1_EIM_03 SR_PRO1_EIM_04 SR_PRO1_EIM_05 SR_PRO1_EIM_06	The EIM module starts signal acquisition via the SDK.
2	Electrical Impedance Module streams electrical impedance data to the GUI.	TC_VOP_02	SR_PRO1_EIM_07	The EIM module starts the data stream via the SDK.
3.1	The technical GUI sends the “Start_Inflation” command via utilizing the Wearable Actuator Module’s SDK. Wearable Actuator Module ensures that upon achieving the required pressure levels, it maintains it.	TC_VOP_03	SR_PRO1_WAM_02 SR_PRO1_WAM_04 SR_PRO1_WAM_06 SR_PRO1_WAM_08	The WAM module responds to the “Start_Inflation” command via the SDK.
3.2	Wearable Actuator Module starts sending pressure values either periodically or on demand to the GUI.	TC_VOP_04	SR_PRO1_WAM_06	The EAC module returns pressure signals to the GUI (computer) via the SDK.
4	Through GUI, the “Stop_Inflation” command is sent to the Wearable Actuator module to start deflation.	TC_VOP_05	SR_PRO1_WAM_06	The WAM responds to deflate

				commands via the SDK.
5	Through GUI, a command is sent to Electrical Impedance Module to stop impedance signal acquisition.	TC_VOP_06	SR_PRO1_EIM_07	The EIM module stops signal acquisition via SDK.

Table 5. High-level workflow of VOP for testing the integration between the AI/ML model and the Central Hub & Intelligence Module.

Work flow step	Description	Test case ID	System requirement	Expected results
6	Central Hub & Intelligence sends Venous Occlusion Plethysmography test data to the AI/ML models.	TC_VOP_07	SR_PRO1_CHI_06	The CHI sends data to the AI module for analysis.
7	AI/ML models process the received data, and returns to the Central Hub & Intelligence a test conclusion, which is either “Suspected for DVT” or “Not Suspected for DVT”	TC_VOP_08	SR_PRO1_CHI_10	The AI/ML model returns calculated results on DVT detection.

3.1.3. High – Level testing of Light Reflection Rheography

The Light Reflection Rheography method is based on the Light Rheography Module (LRM). This is a photometric measurement that determines blood volume changes in an examination segment by analysing its optical properties. The measurement is based on the good absorption of infrared light by haemoglobin (in arterial and venous blood). The method requires vein emptying by performing the “Tip-Toe” leg examination by the user while in a sitting position, before measuring the vein refilling time. In the full integrated ThrombUS+ system, patients will be guided to perform the “Tip-Toe” tests by utilizing the Limb Activity Module for leg activity monitoring and the Extended Reality & Serious Gaming module for guidance. However, at this testing phase the steps for testing the Light Reflection Rheography method is presented in Figure 6. Following these steps enable the evaluation and compatibility of between hardware and software, for this functional method before attempting to integrate it to the final ThrombUS+ system. The testing steps are presented in detail in Table 6.

Figure 6. High level workflow of testing the Light Reflection Rheography subsystem. At this stage the Central Hub & Intelligence module is replaced by technical Graphical User Interfaces for testing purposes.

Table 6. High-level workflow of LRR for testing.

Work flow step	Description	Test case ID	System requirement	Expected results
1	Upon pressing the device's button, the device becomes available for receiving control commands.	TC_LRM_01	SR_PRO1_LRM_01	The LRM module wakes up after USER presses the button.
2	The technical GUI sends the start acquisition command utilizing Light Rheography's Module SDK, and signal acquisition starts.	TC_LRM_02	SR_PRO1_LRM_03	The LRM module starts signal acquisition via the SDK.
3	The Light Rheography Module streams data to the GUI (computer).	TC_LRM_03	SR_PRO1_LRM_03	The LRM module starts the signal stream via the SDK.
4	The technical GUI displays a message for the patient to start the Tip-Toe examination and displays a stop message at the end.	TC_LRM_04	SR_PRO1_LRM_05	The GUI guides the patient to perform Tip-Toe movements.
5	The GUI displays a message for the patient not to move and a countdown timer, while measurements of the venous refilling are acquired.	TC_LRM_05	SR_PRO1_LRM_03	The GUI instructs the patient not to move and displays a countdown for veins to naturally refill.
6	The GUI, utilizing Light Rheography's Module SDK, sends a command to Light Rheography Module to stop signal acquisition.	TC_LRM_06	SR_PRO1_LRM_03	The LRM module stops signal acquisition via the SDK.
7	Upon analysing the acquired data and extracting the refilling parameters, the Light Reflection Module transfers them to the GUI (computer)	TC_LRM_07	SR_PRO1_LRM_06	The LRM calculates parameters of the examination and transfers them to the GUI (computer).

3.1.4. High – Level testing of DVT prevention functional method

The high-level workflow for testing the integration between the Extended Reality & Serious Gaming Module and the Limb Activity Module, which provides the leg activity data is shown below in Figure 7. The high-level testing workflow also includes the Central Hub & Intelligence Module that serves as an intermediate between the other two modules. The Extender Reality & Serious Gaming Module will be utilized to train and guide patients to perform their DVT-prevention rehabilitation exercises, but also motivate them to perform the above-mentioned leg activity exercises via serious gaming. The steps of the workflow and the expected results, which define the "Test Cases" for the DVT prevention functional method are shown in Table 7. The high-level workflow, although it integrates and the core functionality of the DVT prevention method, it does not integration the Light Rheography Module, that it will assess blood flow in real-time during exercises. This integration will take place in the second phase of testing.

Figure 7. High level workflow for the DVT prevention functional working method.

Table 7. High-level workflow of the DVT prevention for testing the integration Limb Activity Module, the Extended Reality & Serious Gaming Module and the Central Hub & Intelligence.

Work flow step	Description	Test case ID	System requirement	Expected results
1.1	Central Hub & Intelligence initializes the Limb Activity Module.	TC_SGM_01	SR_PRO1_LAM_02 SR_PRO1_LAM_03 SR_PRO1_LAM_04 SR_PRO1_LAM_08	The LAM module starts signal acquisition via the SDK.
1.2	Central Hub & Intelligence initializes the Extended Reality & Serious Gaming module.	TC_SGM_02	SR_PRO1_XGM_03 SR_PRO1_XGM_04 SR_PRO1_XGM_06 SR_PRO1_XGM_09	XGM’s user interface loads and runs.
2	Central Hub & Intelligence sends or provides access to the physiotherapy scheme and prerecorded reference exercises for patient training, guidance and use in the serious gaming.	TC_SGM_03	SR_PRO1_XGM_01 SR_PRO1_XGM_02 SR_PRO1_XGM_04 SR_PRO1_XGM_06 SR_PRO1_XGM_07	The XGM loads the prerecorded reference exercises and patients’ personal related data such as prescribed rehabilitation scheme properly.

3.1	Upon requested by the Central Hub & Intelligence, the Limb Activity Module streams leg activity data to the Central Hub & Intelligence.	TC_SGM_04	SR_PRO1_LAM_12 SR_PRO1_LAM_07	The LAM module streams signal data via SDK.
3.2	Central Hub & Intelligence Unit forwards data received by the Limb Activity Module to the Extended Reality & Serious Gaming Module.	TC_SGM_05	SR_PRO1_LAM_12 SR_PRO1_XGM_05 SR_PRO1_XGM_11 SR_PRO1_XGM_12	LAM orientation data are transferred properly to XGM enabling real-time update of the virtual scene based on patients' leg movement.
4	While patient performs exercises, the Extended Reality & Serious Gaming module monitors and displays the patient's movements, compares them to the prerecorded reference exercises and performs continuous activity assessment during serious gaming. During this step, and upon requested by the Central Hub & Intelligence, DVT prevention methods are interrupted, if DVT-monitoring methods should start.	TC_SGM_06	SR_PRO1_LAM_12 SR_PRO1_LAM_05 SR_PRO1_LAM_07 SR_PRO1_XGM_05 SR_PRO1_XGM_06 SR_PRO1_XGM_07 SR_PRO1_XGM_10 SR_PRO1_XGM_11 SR_PRO1_XGM_12	The XGM monitors and assesses in real-time the patient's leg movement providing guidance when required and reports patient's progress.
5	The Extended Reality & Serious Gaming Module periodically transmits reports and analytics to the Central Hub & Intelligence.	TC_SGM_07	SR_PRO1_LAM_07 SR_PRO1_LAM_08 SR_PRO1_XGM_07 SR_PRO1_XGM_08	The XGM module generates session results and reports.
6.1	Upon exercise schema completion or upon user's request, Central Hub & Intelligence sends the termination command to the XGM module.	TC_SGM_08	SR_PRO1_LAM_08 SR_PRO1_XGM_06 SR_PRO1_XGM_08	The XGM module quits the virtual player scene.
6.2	Central Hub & Intelligence Module sends the termination command ("stop_streaming") to the Limb Activity Modules to terminate data streaming and data acquisition.	TC_SGM_09	SR_PRO1_LAM_08	The LAM module responds to commands to stop signal acquisition.

3.1.5. Testing plan for ThrombUS+ integration software

The Central Hub and Intelligence application is a windows-based service and a graphical user interface that integrates all ThrombUS+ subsystems and modules from the software level. The Central Hub & Intelligence module serves as the central node, for synchronizing and controlling the several services required by each functional method and working mode. At this testing phase, the core functionalities of the Central Hub & Intelligence unit will be based, before integrating the various modules to implement the functional methods of the ThrombUS+ device. The test cases provided below verify that every critical capability of the Central Hub & Intelligence as a unit works as intended. Although the intelligence of the Central Hub & Intelligence allows it to perform scheduled tasks autonomously, it also requires user input. Therefore, in the table below (Table 8) each "Test Case" is described by the various steps the user should follow, instead of single steps.

Table 8. Testing steps for the core functionality of the Central Hub & Intelligence module.

Workflow step	Description	Test case ID	System requirement	Expected results
Admin manages the device with a specific PIN code for role switching.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Log in as Admin. 2. Navigate to "Settings" and "Device PIN Management". 3. Select "Add PIN Code". 4. Assign a device, define a PIN, and select the corresponding role (Technician, Clinician, or Patient). 5. Update the created PIN's details (e.g., change PIN or assigned role). 6. Delete the PIN code entry. 	TC_CHI_01	SR_PRO1_CHI_01_01	PIN codes are successfully created, updated, and deleted. Confirmation messages are displayed, and role switching via PIN code functions correctly.
Manage patients.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Login. 2. Go to "Patients" and "Add New Patient". 3. Input patient details and save. 	TC_CHI_02	SR_PRO1_CHI_02_01 SR_PRO1_CHI_03_01	Patient details stored correctly in SQLite. Patient appears in the patient list.
Initialize patient and database record.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Login as medical specialist. 2. Select patient from list. 3. Click Select & Lock. 	TC_CHI_03	SR_PRO1_CHI_03_01	Patient initialized correctly.
Prescription and management of examinations.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Prescribe examinations and physical therapy to a patient. 2. Select and Lock the patient. 3. Check patient schedule and available examinations and exercises. 	TC_CHI_04	SR_PRO1_CHI_04_01	Patient dashboard includes the prescribed examinations and exercises according to the saved prescription plan.
Manage patient health records.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open patient profile. 2. Add or modify health records. 3. Save changes. 	TC_CHI_05	SR_PRO1_CHI_07_01	Health record updated successfully and saved in database.
Patient notifications and alerts.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Trigger examination alerts by abnormal data simulation. 2. Observe patient notification mechanism (popup, audio). 	TC_CHI_06	SR_PRO1_CHI_09_01	Alerts and notifications triggered timely presented clearly.
Historical data and analytics.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Navigate to analytics. 2. Select patient history view. 	TC_CHI_07	SR_PRO1_CHI_14_01	Historical data presented accurately, analytics relevant and correct.

Application alarms and notifications.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Simulate critical conditions. 2. Observe alarms and notifications. 	TC_CHI_08	SR_PRO1_CHI_16_01	Alarms trigger appropriately; notifications are clearly visible/audible.
Export data functionality.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Select completed examination. 2. Choose “Export Data”. 	TC_CHI_09	SR_PRO1_CHI_19_01	Data are exported correct in the specified format (CSV/Excel), and they are accessible and readable.
Anonymized research data export.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open settings. 2. Selected datasets. 3. Choose “Export Anonymized Data”. 		SR_PRO1_CHI_20_01	Data anonymized effectively (no personal info). Exported correctly.
Interoperability with the Health Information System (HIS).	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Trigger data sync with HIS. 	TC_CHI_10	SR_PRO1_CHI_22_01	Patient’s data are updated according to data on the Health Information System.

3.2. System readiness testing plan

3.2.1. Readiness testing of the ThrombUS+ DVT monitoring subsystems

The main goal of the readiness testing of the DVT monitoring subsystems (CDUS, VOP, LRR) is to demonstrate that they are safe to use (see subsection 3.3.3) and effective in detecting changes in venous blood flow, presumably due to thrombus formation.

Readiness testing of the CDUS subsystem will be conducted in its three working modes: Imaging, Monitoring, and Analysis. The Imaging mode enables manual operation of the system as a standard ultrasound machine. The Monitoring mode includes initial calibration across the full range of actuator-driven compression, after which the system operates in an operator-independent mode. In this mode, the CDUS subsystem can execute a standard compression ultrasonography protocol and repeat it intermittently at predefined time intervals. The final mode, Analysis, allows the operator to visually evaluate the data collected during different monitoring sessions. For testing purposes, both commercial and newly developed phantoms (within the ThrombUS+ project) will be used for laboratory evaluation of the CDUS subsystem’s readiness.

Readiness testing of the VOP and LRR subsystems will involve healthy volunteers, as no suitable phantom currently exists for testing these methods with or without mimicking DVT. Within the project a simulation methodology of DVT-like hemodynamic alterations was developed by controlled external thigh compression, which allows for testing different conditions (e.g., DVT simulation). To demonstrate subsystem readiness, only several subjects are needed; therefore, healthy volunteers from the project team, who are fully aware and informed about the tests and data collection, will be included. VOP and LRR tests are non-invasive, and all of the hardware is produced following design-by-compliance principles; therefore, there is no inherent risk. Additionally, an appropriate consent form will be signed.

For the fully integrated ThrombUS system, risk analysis was performed and documented in Table 6. Based on the planned tests in the system readiness testing phase for the non-invasive LRR, VOP, and CDUS subsystems', the following risks are foreseen along with their mitigation strategy.

Table 9. Risks and mitigation for the non-invasive subsystems during readiness testing phases.

No	Risk	Severity	Probability	Probability after mitigation	Mitigation
1	Leakage current	S4	L2	L1	Isolation transformer or/and batteries are used. Systems isolated from electrical network.
2	Prolonged pressure	S3	L2	L1	1. Pressure release timer coded in firmware. 2. Normally-open exit valves release in case of error.
3	Excessive pressure	S3	L2	L1	1. Over-pressure sensing and release system coded in firmware. 2. Normally-open exit valves release.
4	Skin irritation and sensitization	S1	L2	L1	1. Limited exposure time. 2. Biocompatible materials. 3. Defined cleaning procedures.
5	Ultrasound radiation too high	S3	L2	L1	Ultrasound acoustic emission measurements were performed and not exceed safety limits.

Additional information on the specific tests can be found in Annex 1.

3.2.2. Readiness testing of the ThrombUS+ DVT prevention subsystem

To implement the DVT prevention method, the Limb Activity Module, the Extended Reality & Serious Gaming Module and the Central Hub & Intelligence module should be integrated. The integration of these modules is tested during the system integration testing phase. However, for the final functional working method the Light Rheography Module must also be integrated. The integration of all these modules will offer the advantage of not only lower limb activity monitoring to guide and motivate patients, but it will also allow the assessment of blood volume changes providing real-time evaluation of exercise effectiveness. Therefore, the tests at this testing phase will focus on the integration and combined operation of all the above-mentioned modules.

Additional information on the specific tests can be found in Annex 1.

3.2.3. Safety, data security, privacy, and the overall robustness of the system

Patient and device safety testing will encompass biocompatibility testing of all skin-contact materials according to ISO 10993 standards, with particular attention to prolonged exposure scenarios given the continuous monitoring application. Maximal pressure by the actuator and electrical safety testing will verify compliance with IEC 60601-1 medical device standards, including leakage current measurements, insulation resistance, and protection against electrical hazards. Thermal safety assessments will ensure surface temperatures remain within safe limits during extended operation, with testing under various ambient conditions and usage scenarios. The compliance to the standard IEC 60601-2 specific to ultrasonic medical devices, which defines requirements on Thermal Index (TI) and Mechanical Index (MI) related to potential thermal and mechanical hazards will be tested. Particular requirements for the basic safety and essential

performance of ultrasonic medical diagnostic and monitoring equipment (IEC 60601-2-37:2007, IEC 60601-2-37:2007/AMD1:2015) will be met.

Ultrasound exposure testing will validate that acoustic output remains well within standards-established limits for diagnostic ultrasound devices, with specific attention to cumulative exposure during continuous intermittent monitoring. Emergency safety protocols will be tested to ensure the device can be safely removed in urgent medical situations, and fail-safe mechanisms will be validated to prevent false alarms that could lead to unnecessary medical interventions.

Cybersecurity testing of the ThrombUS+ system will follow state-of-the-art guidelines, aligned with the BSI-CS 132⁴ recommendations for network-connected medical devices, as well as other complementary European guidelines, including MDCG 2019-16⁵ on cybersecurity for medical devices, IEC 62304⁶ for software lifecycle security, and applicable principles from ISO/IEC 27001⁷ and ETSI EN 303 645⁸. Given that ThrombUS+ operates as a set of local services running on a dedicated standalone computer (laptop), communicating with wearable devices over a private, secured wireless network (with WPA2 or WPA3 encryption protocol⁹), the cybersecurity testing will focus on protecting system integrity, patient safety, and data confidentiality within this specific setup. The main cybersecurity testing activities will include:

- **System Hardening:** Tests will ensure only essential services are active on the laptop, with unused ports and protocols disabled. Secure configurations (e.g., strong authentication, encrypted storage, and communication) will be validated.
- **Wireless Network Security:** The proprietary wireless network connecting wearable modules to the laptop will be tested to confirm encryption, access control, and protection against unauthorized connections or interference.
- **Access Control and Authentication:** Role-based access controls will be tested to ensure only authorized users (e.g., medical personnel) can access system functions. Password/Pin-based management and user session security will be validated.
- **Secure Update Mechanisms:** The process for updating ThrombUS+ software on the laptop and modules will be tested to ensure authenticity checks and protection against unauthorized modifications.
- **Incident Detection and Logging:** System logs and alerts will be tested to confirm that critical events — such as failed login attempts or suspicious wireless activity — are properly recorded and communicated for prompt action.

Cybersecurity testing will ensure that the complete ThrombUS+ system, including software, wearable devices, and wireless communication, is resilient against cyber threats before clinical deployment.

⁴ German Federal Office for Information Security, Cyber Security Requirements for Network-Connected Medical Devices, November 2018 [Online]. BSI-CS 132 | Version 1.1. Available: https://www.bsi.bund.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/EN/BSI/ICS/Medical_Devices_CS-E_132.pdf

⁵ Medical Device Coordination Group, 2019. MDCG 2019-16-Guidance on Cybersecurity for medical devices. European Commission. Available: https://health.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-01/md_cybersecurity_en.pdf

⁶ International Electrotechnical Commission, 2006. CEI/IEC 62304: Medical device software—Software life cycle processes. Geneva.

⁷ International Electrotechnical Commission, 2022. ISO/IEC 27001: Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection — Information security management systems — Requirements. Geneva.

⁸ European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), 2024. ETSI EN 303 645 (v3.1.3): Cyber Security for Consumer Internet of Things: Baseline Requirements, France.

⁹ IEEE 802 LAN/MAN Standards Committee, 2009. IEEE Standard for Information technology - Telecommunication and information exchange between systems - Local and metropolitan area networks - Specific requirements - Part 11: Wireless LAN Medium Access Control (MAC) and Physical Layer (PHY) Specifications Amendment 5: Enhancements for Higher Throughput. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IEEESTD.2009.5307322>

Privacy compliance testing will verify that the ThrombUS+ system adheres to GDPR and relevant data protection regulations. This includes systematic testing of data minimization, patient consent mechanisms, and data retention controls. Role-based access control will be tested to ensure that only authorized healthcare personnel can access sensitive information, with effective prevention of unauthorized access. Data anonymization and pseudonymization processes will be validated to confirm they protect patient identity while preserving the clinical and research value of the exported data.

AI algorithm robustness will be tested using edge case scenarios, and data drift detection to ensure consistent performance across diverse patient populations and clinical conditions. Communication reliability testing will validate system performance under various network conditions, including intermittent connectivity scenarios common in healthcare environments.

Battery life testing will verify continuous operation duration under various usage patterns, with validation of low-power alerts. Finally, the robustness of the system will be tested by simulating long-term (72h) continuous/intermittent monitoring in the lab environment.

Additional information on the specific tests can be found in Annex 1.

4. Concluding remarks

The D6.2 deliverable describes rigorous pre-clinical testing methodology and designs of a comprehensive test plan to demonstrate that the ThrombUS+ system meets the requirements identified in T2.3 and T6.2 and also complies with relevant regulations and standards from T2.2. The methodology includes the general testing process, documentation procedures, and systematic handling of testing failures with design feedback mechanisms. The deliverable focuses on the workflow functioning of integrated beta-prototypes, namely four independent subsystems enabling the entire ThrombUS+ system. The test plan specifies the types of tests to be conducted, the necessary equipment and instruments, and organizational requirements for implementation. Comprehensive pre-clinical tests assess ThrombUS+ safety and potential adverse effects, provide data to support progression to human clinical trials, and create the basis for regulatory review and approval.

Annex 1 - System readiness testing plan

Annex 1 – System Readiness Tests

During this testing phase the whole integrated system will be tested. All methods and working modes will be implemented and tested strictly using the Central Hub & Intelligence module.

1. Readiness testing for the Compression Duplex Ultrasonography DVT monitoring method

Table 10. System readiness tests for the Compression Duplex Ultrasonography subsystem.

Test Case ID	Working mode	Related System Requirement(s)	Test steps	Expected results
TC_CDUS_12	Imaging	SR_PRO1_CHI_10	1. Place ultrasound probe with gel on phantom.	1. Ultrasound imaging starts from Central Hub & Intelligence.
		SR_PRO1_CHI_17	2. Start ultrasound imaging from the Central Hub & Intelligence.	2. Ultrasound parameters are successfully changed.
		SR_PRO1_CHI_18		
		SR_PRO1_CHI_21	3. Adjust imaging settings using the Central Hub & Intelligence application.	3. Ultrasound images of adequate quality are displayed in real time in the Central Hub & Intelligence application.
		SR_PRO1_USM_04		
		SR_PRO1_USM_08		
SR_PRO1_USM_13				
SR_PRO1_USM_18	4. Start imaging from Central Hub & Intelligence application	4. Image is frozen and displayed in the Central Hub & Intelligence application.		
SR_PRO1_USM_21				
TC_CDUS_13	Monitoring	SR_PRO1_CHI_02	1. Mount the Wearable Ultrasound Device on a phantom.	1. Calibration completed successfully.
		SR_PRO1_CHI_03		2. Monitoring plan and required settings set successfully.
		SR_PRO1_CHI_04	2. Start calibration process.	3. Monitoring session starts according to the schedule.
		SR_PRO1_CHI_06		4. Central Hub & Intelligence feeds ultrasound images and pressure levels to the AI/ML models and AI/ML models reply with the inference results and the decisions.
		SR_PRO1_CHI_09		
		SR_PRO1_CHI_10		
SR_PRO1_CHI_16	3. Schedule the monitoring plan by, set	5. Measurements occur at set intervals.		
SR_PRO1_WAM_02				
SR_PRO1_WAM_05				
SR_PRO1_WAM_06				
SR_PRO1_WAM_08				

		SR_PRO1_WAM_15 SR_PRO1_WAM_16 SR_PRO1_WAM_06 SR_PRO1_USM_08 SR_PRO1_USM_09 SR_PRO1_USM_13 SR_PRO1_USM_21	the frequency and the total time of intermittent monitoring, through the Central Hub & Intelligence application.	6. WAM compressions occur successfully.
			4. Initiate the autonomous monitoring plan through the Central Hub & Intelligence unit application.	7. AI-based image parameters are collected.
			5. Simulate DVT.	8. Tissue compression stops based on AI/ML model decision or if the maximum allowed pressure level threshold achieved.
				9. Central Hub & Intelligence reports the results of the examination and triggers the alerts if DVT is presence.
				10. Monitoring is terminated when scheduled plan is completed successfully and the whole monitoring session is saved to the database. If monitoring is terminated unexpectedly the respective errors should be logged successfully.
TC_CDUS_13	Analysis	SR_PRO1_CHI_02 SR_PRO1_CHI_14 SR_PRO1_USM_15 SR_PRO1_USM_19	1. User selects "Analysis" in the Central Hub & Intelligence application	1. "Analysis" interface loads and works properly.
			2. Selects session from monitoring history.	2. A list with all the available exercises performed for the specific patient is displayed. Examinations of interest can be selected for further inspection.
			3. User selects AI-estimated parameters to show as trends.	3. Selected parameters are shown as trends.
			4. User views trends and selects examination of interest.	4. Selected examination of interest is opened.
			5. User reviews recordings of the selected examination.	5. Recording of selected examination is replayed along with the AI/ML model decisions.

2. Readiness testing for the Venous Occlusion Plethysmography DVT monitoring method

Table 11. System readiness tests for the Venous Occlusion Plethysmography subsystem.

Test Case ID	Working mode	Related System Requirement(s)	Test steps	Expected results
TC_VOP_09	Measurement	SR_PR01_CHI_01 SR_PR01_CHI_03 SR_PR01_CHI_10 SR_PR01_CHI_17 SR_PR01_CHI_21 SR_PR01_WAM_02 SR_PR01_WAM_03 SR_PR01_WAM_08 SR_PR01_WAM_15 SR_PR01_WAM_16 SR_PR01_EIM_07 SR_PR01_EIM_14 SR_PR01_EIM_15 SR_PR01_EIM_17	1. Mount the Electrical Impedance and the Wearable Actuator modules.	1. The signal is of adequate quality for electrical impedance measurements and DVT-related parameter extraction.
			2. Start streaming electrical impedance signals to the Central Hub & Intelligence unit to decide if signal is of adequate quality.	2. The Venous Occlusion Plethysmography method starts. The cuff starts to inflate and reaches the desired pressure levels. Electrical impedance measurements are streamed to the Central Hub & Intelligence module for logging.
			3. Initiate a single operator-dependend examination of Venous Occlusion Plethysmography.	3. After measurements are finished, the cuff deflates and electrical impedance data streaming stops. Data are analysed and DVT-related parameters are extracted.
				4. The Central Hub & Intelligence module sends the acquired data to the AI/ML model for parameter interpretation and decision making.
				5. Central Hub & Intelligence unit stores the whole examination along the analysed data and AI/ML decisions.
TC_VOP_10	Monitoring	SR_PR01_CHI_01 SR_PR01_CHI_02 SR_PR01_CHI_03 SR_PR01_CHI_04 SR_PR01_CHI_05 SR_PR01_CHI_06 SR_PR01_CHI_09 SR_PR01_CHI_10 SR_PR01_CHI_13 SR_PR01_WAM_02 SR_PR01_WAM_03 SR_PR01_WAM_08 SR_PR01_WAM_15 SR_PR01_WAM_16 SR_PR01_EIM_07 SR_PR01_EIM_14 SR_PR01_EIM_15 SR_PR01_EIM_17	1. Mount the Electrical Impedance and the Wearable Actuator modules.	1. Monitoring session starts according to the schedule.
			2. Start streaming electrical impedance signals to the Central Hub & Intelligence unit to decide if signal is of adequate quality.	2. The Venous Occlusion Plethysmography method starts. The cuff starts to inflate and reaches the desired pressure levels. Electrical impedance measurements are streamed to the Central Hub & Intelligence module for logging.
			3. Schedule the monitoring plan by, setting the frequency and the total time of intermittent monitoring, through the Central Hub & Intelligence application.	3. After measurements are finished, the cuff deflates and electrical impedance data streaming stops. Data are analysed and DVT-related parameters are extracted.

			4. Initiate the autonomous monitoring plan through the Central Hub & Intelligence unit application.	4. The Central Hub & Intelligence module sends the acquired data to the AI/ML model for parameter interpretation and decision making.
				5. Central Hub & Intelligence unit reports the examination results and stores the whole examination along the analysed data and AI/ML decisions.
				6. Central Hub & Intelligence triggers alerts if DVT is detected.
				7. Operator-independent monitoring is terminated when scheduled plan is completed successfully and the whole monitoring session is saved to the database. If monitoring is terminated unexpectedly the respective errors should be logged successfully.
TC_VOP_11	Analysis	SR_PR01_CHI_02 SR_PR01_CHI_13 SR_PR01_CHI_14 SR_PR01_CHI_15 SR_PR01_WAM_15	1. User selects "Analysis" in the Central Hub & Intelligence application	1. "Analysis" interface loads and works properly.
			2. Selects session from monitoring history.	2. A list with all the available exercises performed for the specific patient is displayed. Examinations of interest can be selected for further inspection.
			3. User selects AI-estimated parameters to show as trends.	3. Selected parameters are shown as trends.
			4. User views trends and selects examination of interest.	4. Selected examination of interest is opened.
			5. User reviews recordings of the selected examination.	5. Recording of selected examination is replayed along with the AI/ML model decisions.

3. Readiness testing for the Light Reflection Rheography DVT monitoring method

Table 12. System readiness tests for the Light Reflection Rheography subsystem.

Test Case ID	Working mode	Related System Requirement(s)	Test steps	Expected results
TC_LRR_08	Measurement	SR_PRO1_CHI_01 SR_PRO1_CHI_03 SR_PRO1_CHI_10 SR_PRO1_CHI_17 SR_PRO1_CHI_21 SR_PRO1_LRM_08 SR_PRO1_LRM_09 SR_PRO1_XGM_01 SR_PRO1_XGM_06 SR_PRO1_XGM_12	1. Place the Light Reflection Rheography Module and the Limb Activity Module.	1. Signal is of adequate quality for the Light Reflection Rheography method. 2. The Central Intelligence Unit utilizes the Extended Reality & Serious Gaming and the Limb Activity Modules to assist user acquire proper positioning. Patient is visually guided to perform the “Tip-Toe” examination and a countdown timer is displayed.
			2. Initiate the operator-dependent Light Reflection Rheography working mode through the Central Hub & Intelligence application.	3. Light Reflection Rheography data are acquired properly and transmitted to the Central Hub & Intelligence. Received data are visualized and stored properly by the Central Hub & Intelligence application. 4. Acquired data are analysed and DVT-related parameters are extracted and transmitted to Central Hub & Intelligence and stored.
TC_LRR_09	Monitoring	SR_PRO1_CHI_01 SR_PRO1_CHI_02 SR_PRO1_CHI_03 SR_PRO1_CHI_04 SR_PRO1_CHI_05 SR_PRO1_CHI_06 SR_PRO1_CHI_09 SR_PRO1_CHI_13 SR_PRO1_LRM_08 SR_PRO1_LRM_09 SR_PRO1_XGM_01 SR_PRO1_XGM_06 SR_PRO1_XGM_12	1. Place the Light Reflection Rheography Module and the Limb Activity Module.	1. Monitoring session starts according to the schedule. 2. The Light Reflection Rheography method starts. Light reflection measurements are streamed to the Central Hub & Intelligence.
			2. Schedule the monitoring plan by, setting the frequency and the total time of intermittent monitoring, through the Central Hub & Intelligence application.	3. The Central Intelligence Unit utilizes the Extended Reality & Serious Gaming and the Limb Activity Modules to assist user acquire proper positioning. Patient is visually guided to perform the “Tip-Toe” examination and a countdown timer is displayed. 4. Acquired data are analysed and DVT-related parameters are extracted and transmitted to Central Hub & Intelligence and stored. 5. Central Hub & Intelligence unit stores the whole examination along the analysed data and AI/ML decisions.

			3. Initiate the autonomous monitoring plan through the Central Hub & Intelligence unit application.	6. Monitoring is terminated when scheduled plan is completed successfully and the whole monitoring session is saved to the database. If monitoring is terminated unexpectedly the respective errors should be logged successfully.
TC_LRR_10	Analysis	SR_PRO1_CHI_02 SR_PRO1_CHI_13 SR_PRO1_CHI_14 SR_PRO1_CHI_15	1. User selects "Analysis" in the Central Hub & Intelligence application	1. "Analysis" interface loads and works properly.
			2. Selects session from monitoring history.	2. A list with all the available exercises performed for the specific patient is displayed. Examinations of interest can be selected for further inspection.
			3. User views trends and selects examination of interest.	3. Selected parameters are shown as trends.
			4. User reviews recordings of the selected examination.	4. Selected examination of interest is opened.

4. Readiness testing for the DVT prevention method

Table 13. System readiness tests for the DVT-prevention method.

Test Case ID	Working mode	Related System Requirement(s)	Test steps	Expected results			
TC_SGM_10	Prevention	SR_PR01_CHI_01 SR_PR01_CHI_02 SR_PR01_CHI_03 SR_PR01_CHI_04 SR_PR01_CHI_05 SR_PR01_CHI_12 SR_PR01_LRM_08 SR_PR01_LAM_07 SR_PR01_LAM_11 SR_PR01_LAM_20 SR_PR01_XGM_01 SR_PR01_XGM_02 SR_PR01_XGM_04 SR_PR01_XGM_05 SR_PR01_XGM_06 SR_PR01_XGM_07 SR_PR01_XGM_08 SR_PR01_XGM_12	1. Prescribe a rehabilitation scheme and schedule the rehabilitation plan for the specific patient using the prerecorded reference exercises.	1. The Extended Reality & Serious Gaming Module loads. The prescription scheme is loaded properly within the Extended Reality and Serious Gaming Module.			
					2. The Limb Activity Module is initiated, and limb activity data are streamed to the Central Hub & Intelligence unit. Data are forwarded in real-time to the Extended Reality & Serious Gaming Module.		
			2. Wear the Limb Activity Module to monitor leg activity.	3. The Light Reflection Rheography module is initiated, and data are transfer to the Central Hub & Intelligence.			
				4. User can select the “Training” mode to learn how to perform the prescribed exercises and the “Exercise” mode to perform the rehabilitation exercises.			
			3. Once prompt by the Central Hub & Intelligence application, initiate the Extended Reality and Serious Gaming module.	5. Leg activity is visualized properly in the Extended Reality & Serious Gaming environment.			
				6. Guidance is provided visually when deviation from the reference exercises is detected.			
			4. Interact with the Extended Reality & Serious Gaming user interface and navigate to the “Training” mode or the “Exercise” mode.	7. Activity data, performed exercises and light rheography data are transferred to the Central Hub & Intelligence and stored periodically and properly.			
			5. Terminate the Extended Reality & Serious Gaming method for DVT-prevention.	8. Extended Reality & Serious Gaming, Limb Activity and Light Rheography Modules, terminate successfully upon requested and all activity and exercises-related data are transferred and stored successfully.			
			TC_SGM_10	Prevention	SR_PR01_CHI_01 SR_PR01_CHI_02 SR_PR01_CHI_03 SR_PR01_CHI_04 SR_PR01_CHI_05	1. Prescribe a rehabilitation scheme for the specific patient using the prerecorded reference exercises.	1. The Extended Reality & Serious Gaming Module loads. The prescription scheme is loaded properly within the Extended Reality and Serious Gaming Module.

		SR_PR01_CHI_12 SR_PR01_LRM_08 SR_PR01_LAM_07 SR_PR01_LAM_11 SR_PR01_LAM_20 SR_PR01_XGM_01 SR_PR01_XGM_02 SR_PR01_XGM_04 SR_PR01_XGM_05 SR_PR01_XGM_06 SR_PR01_XGM_07 SR_PR01_XGM_08 SR_PR01_XGM_09 SR_PR01_XGM_12	2. The Limb Activity Module is initiated, and limb activity data are streamed to the Central Hub & Intelligence unit. Data are forwarded in real-time to the Extended Reality & Serious Gaming Module. 2. Wear the Limb Activity Module to monitor leg activity. 3. Interact with the Extended Reality & Serious Gaming user interface and navigate to the “Serious Gaming” mode. 4. Terminate the Extended Reality & Serious Gaming method for DVT-prevention.	3. The Light Reflection Rheography module is initiated, and data are transfer to the Central Hub & Intelligence. 4. Users select the “Gaming” mode to start interacting with the serious gaming environment. 5. Leg activity is visualized properly in the Extended Reality & Serious Gaming environment. 6. Activity data, performed exercises and light rheography data are transferred to the Central Hub & Intelligence and stored periodically and properly. 7. Extended Reality & Serious Gaming, Limb Activity and Light Rheography Modules, terminate successfully upon requested and all activity and exercises-related data and game progress are transferred and stored successfully.
TC_SGM_10	N/A	SR_PR01_CHI_01 SR_PR01_CHI_02 SR_PR01_CHI_03 SR_PR01_CHI_04 SR_PR01_CHI_05 SR_PR01_CHI_12 SR_PR01_LAM_07 SR_PR01_LAM_11 SR_PR01_LAM_20 SR_PR01_XGM_01 SR_PR01_XGM_02 SR_PR01_XGM_03 SR_PR01_XGM_06 SR_PR01_XGM_12	1. Wear the Limb Activity Module to monitor leg activity. 2. Interact with the Extended Reality & Serious Gaming user interface and navigate to the “Add new exercise” mode.	1. The Limb Activity Module transmit data to the Central Hub & Intelligence and data are forwarded to the Extended Reality & Serious Gaming Module for lower limb visualization 2. Performed exercise is recorded successfully. Recorded metadata that describe the exercise are recorded successfully. 3. The new recorded exercises is available in the list with the reference exercises and can be used in the rehabilitation scheme.

5. Readiness testing for the Central Hub & Intelligence module

Table 14. System readiness tests for the Central Hub & Intelligence module.

Test Case ID	Working mode	Related System Requirement(s)	Test steps	Expected results
TC_CHI_10	Prevention	SR_PR01_CHI_03 SR_PR01_CHI_04 SR_PR01_CHI_05 SR_PR01_CHI_06	1. Select and lock a patient with a known prescription plan.	1. Examination automatically initiated and streaming data appears correctly.
			2. Confirm automatic initialization is enabled.	
			3. Observe if examination starts without manual intervention.	
TC_CHI_11	N/A	SR_PR01_CHI_02 SR_PR01_CHI_06 SR_PR01_CHI_15	1. Monitor background processes via logging.	1. Background processes stable, logging accurate, data consistency maintained.
			2. Ensure continuous data synchronization (UI updates, sensor data, DB writes).	
TC_CHI_12	Monitoring	SR_PR01_CHI_07 SR_PR01_CHI_08	1. Run examination.	1. DVT risk updated correctly.
			2. Observe real-time DVT risk visualization in the UI.	
TC_CHI_13	Imaging Measurement Monitoring	SR_PR01_CHI_11	1. Start an examination.	1. Examination halts immediately, clear UI and audio indicators activated.
			2. Press emergency stop simulating an abnormal scenario.	
TC_CHI_14	Imaging Measurement Monitoring	SR_PR01_CHI_10	1. Start an examination.	1. Progress visualized correctly, updating continuously until completion.
			2. Monitor UI visualization of progress and data collection status.	
TC_CHI_15	Prevention	SR_PR01_CHI_12	1. Begin the DVT-prevention method.	1. Examination halts immediately, clear UI and audio indicators activated.
			2. Press emergency stop simulating an abnormal scenario.	
TC_CHI_16	Imaging, Measurement, Monitoring, Prevention	SR_PR01_CHI_13 SR_PR01_CHI_14 SR_PR01_CHI_15	1. Start multiple examinations.	1. Module responsive, data recorded accurately, and UI reflecting session status clearly.
			2. Observe status tracking dashboard.	
TC_CHI_17	Analysis	SR_PR01_CHI_15 SR_PR01_CHI_16	1. Login as medical expert.	1. Dashboard accurately reflects current examination and patient conditions in real-time.
			2. Access real-time monitoring dashboard.	
TC_CHI_18		SR_PR01_CHI_17	1. Select patient.	

	Imaging, Measurement		2. Manually initiate an examination.	1. Examination starts upon manual action, with correct patient and parameters loaded.
TC_CHI_19	Imaging, Measurement	SR_PR01_CHI_21	1. Open settings.	1. Customized settings saved and correctly applied during data collection.
			2. Modify data collection settings.	
			3. Perform examination with new settings.	

6. Connectivity, data security and privacy of the fully integrated ThrombUS+ system

Table 15. Risks and mitigation for the non-invasive subsystems during readiness testing phases.

Test Case ID	Priority Functions & Features Tested	Related System Requirement(s)	Test steps	Expected results
TC_SEC_01	System Hardening	SR_PRO1_CHI_07 SR_PRO1_CHI_03 SR_PRO1_CHI_06	Tests will ensure only essential services are active on the laptop, with unused ports and protocols disabled. Secure configurations (e.g., strong authentication, encrypted storage, and communication) will be validated.	Pass/Fail
TC_SEC_02	Wireless Network Security	SR_PRO1_CHI_19 SR_PRO1_CHI_22 SR_PRO1_USM_17 SR_PRO1_EIM_11	The proprietary wireless network connecting wearable modules to the laptop will be tested to confirm encryption, access control, and protection against unauthorized connections or interference.	Pass/Fail
TC_SEC_03	Access Control and Authentication	SR_PRO1_CHI_01 SR_PRO1_CHI_02 SR_PRO1_CHI_03 SR_PRO1_USM_09	Role-based access controls will be tested to ensure only authorized users (e.g., medical personnel) can access system functions. Password/Pin-based management and user session security will be validated.	Pass/Fail
TC_SEC_04	Secure Update Mechanisms	N/A	The process for updating ThrombUS+ software on the laptop and modules will be tested to ensure authenticity checks and protection against unauthorized modifications.	Pass/Fail
TC_SEC_05	Incident Detection and Logging	SR_PRO1_CHI_01 SR_PRO1_CHI_11 SR_PRO1_CHI_12 SR_PRO1_CHI_03	System logs and alerts will be tested to confirm that critical events — such as failed login attempts or suspicious wireless activity — are properly recorded and communicated for prompt action.	Pass/Fail

TC_PRI_01	Data anonymization and pseudonymization	SR_PRO1_CHI_20 SR_PRO1_CHI_15 SR_PRO1_CHI_08 SR_PRO1_CHI_02 SR_PRO1_XGM_02	It will be validated to confirm they protect patient identity while preserving the clinical and research value of the exported data.	Pass/Fail
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Annex 2 - Testing report documentation file template

ThrombUS+ Testing Report Documentation (Version 1.0, Date 2025-06-30)										
System integration testing phase										
Test Case ID	Test description	Related Requirement(s)	Expected results	Preconditions	Test steps	Actual test steps	Pass/Fail	Report	Tested by	Date
TC_CDUS_XX										
TC_VOP_XX										
TC_LRR_XX										
TC_XGM_XX										
System readiness testing phase										
Test Case ID	Test description	Related Requirement(s)	Expected results	Preconditions	Test steps	Actual test steps	Pass/Fail	Report	Tested by	Date
TC_CDUS_XX										
TC_VOP_XX										
TC_LRR_XX										
TC_XGM_XX										
TC_CHI_XX										